

An Intelligent IoT Based Hydroponics for Smart Soilless Agriculture

Sivakumar G¹, Selvarasu S², Selvi C³

¹Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Muthayammal Engineering College, Nammakal- 637408, Tamil Nadu.

²Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Muthayammal Engineering College, Nammakal- 637408, Tamil Nadu.

³Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Muthayammal Engineering College, Nammakal- 637408, Tamil Nadu.

Abstract: Agriculture plays a major function on improving the financial system of the United States. modern-day farming technique like Hydroponics is in rise which is soilless farming tradition and the flowers have been grown with the help of nutrient solutions. The Aquicultural device can be learned via a device mastering technique like artificial Neural Networks (ANN). net of things (IoT) allows device to device conversation and monitoring the hydroponic arrangement and intelligently. This painting is evolved an wise IoT based hydroponic device by applying ANN. The hydroponic system imparting a sensor like temperature, humidity, suitable manage over the sprinkler and water waft for the aquicultural atmosphere primarily based at the multiple input parameters collected from sensors.

INTRODUCTION

The hydroponics is the manner of vegetation cultivation in water. it is a subcategory of hydroculture and is a useful approach of developing flowers without soil. through this technique, roots absorb the vitamins found in water and fulfil their boom requirement. moreover, via this approach, you possibly can develop flowers in liquid, sand or gravel via clearly adding a few vitamins to it. on this machine, it can't be clean to screen a flowers boom parameter of humidity, PH degree, temperature, water flow and so forth with the aid of a human for everytime. to control and screen this gadget, the fairly advanced system mastering (ML) algorithms may be applied in a few papers. The ML is a subset of modern technology that allows in offering computer systems skill to perform moves on its very own after being skilled for a particular undertaking, leading, for a system to think like a human mind, it has first to think and learn like a person. Artificial intelligence thinks from the past reviews and past records this is showing to and based on that the human being takes choice for the destiny. The ML technique has numerous uses inside the discipline of aquiculture near governing the plant growth, optimization of sensor values of the Nutrient solution. In terms of programming in controlling aquicultural environs, those ML procedures were now not able to gain a high level of correctness, and also those algorithms had been tested in the direction of controlling few parameters in a hydroponic surroundings. consequently the cloud server is used. The cloud based aquiculture gadget for controlling more than one parameters of the hydroponic environment closer to presenting suitable manage motion. all these prompted toward developing with an intelligent and computerized cloud based aquiculture gadget with better intelligence and accuracy. on this paintings, the clever farming for monitoring and controlling the environmental occasions consisting of PH stages, temperature, water waft degree, and humidity. these parameters are controlled by way of using IOT generation. The rest of the paper organised as: related works is mentioned in segment 2 and the proposed method is defined in section 3. The hardware description is offered in segment four and subsequently the paintings is concluded in section five.

RELATED WORKS

Fitria et al planned a remembered control gadget for tank-farming plants, comprising of a water pH oversee machine and a supplement answer control gadget.

This framework is in like manner in view of the net of things (IoT), wherein realities obtained from pH sensors and EC sensors may be handled by a microcontroller and afterward shipped off the IoT Antares stage through the to be had verbal trade modules.

Al-Gharibi et al gave a contemporary gadget to observing boundaries like temperature, stickiness, water temperature, TDS, pH, and light profundity through c084d04ddacadd4b971ae3d98fecfb2a inside the Blynk stage. It guarantees a likelihood to develop types of plants over the year with out the limitations forced by utilizing climate.

John et al concentrated on IoT based programmed hydroponics structures. we will see numerous programmed capacities here, which incorporates: robotized taking care of machine, water incredible oversee gadget, programmed lighting apparatuses gadget for blossoms, temperature and mugginess control and so on. In hydroponics device the wireless meals(pellets) assumes a vital part inside the water wiwireless.

Arora et al planned a programmed dosing device in Hydroponics might be checked and controlled with the assistance of machine dominating calculations like Deep Neural Networks. we can talk how IoT permits discussion among machines and furthermore notice the boundaries which meaningfully affect plant increment inside the tank-farming device.

Nugroho et al proposed a Deep Neural organization (DNN) as prescient control to characterize proper control measures and contrast their appraisal with manual control. With 4000 control measurements got from oneself advanced IoT machine, a sort is done the use of DNN to give a biggest adaptation that is then completed in the IoT framework to are expecting the appropriate control activity for aqua-farming.

Sahu et al did a gadget acquiring information on arrangement inside the discipline. All sensors(pH Sensor, DHT eleven Sensor, DS18B20 Sensor) detecting their individual boundaries which may be expected to examine for following of vegetation.

Goodbyes et al gave the plan, and execution of a wise, low-charge IoT-essentially based oversee and observing gadget for tank-farming nurseries. The device depends on three types of sensor hubs: the fundamental (handle) hub is liable for controlling the siphon, following the wi-top notch of the water in the nursery and conglomerating and sending current realities from the slave hubs.

Quach et al evaluated the ability for Microgrid Supported Open Hydroponic Crop Cultivation (MSOHCC) to be a compelling enhancement to current food insurance projects in SIDS.

López-Tejeida et al ventured to reusing those nutrients is to get a genuine proportion of nitrogen from hydroponics and hydroponics wastewater after this the subsequent stage is to figure out which kind of strategy will be utilized to lessen the supplements to a fitting degree.

Sahara et al planned aqua-farming creating media mechanically fueled through sun cells. sun based cells are utilized as a power supply to modify the inventory of water, water pH, supplements, and other additional components required by utilizing aqua-farming verdure. all together that it can shop on the utilization of electrical strength, it will be overseen consequently that is modified into the Arduino, and the readings on the gadget are shown at the lcd as a checking machine.

Dutta et al thought about the yield and the development of plants, a wi-ficientwireless strategy is accommodated the right increment of vegetation with significantly less water use and least need of nutrients the utilization of IOT fundamentally based methods.

Friuli et al provided four.zero-orientated acquaponic contraption that incorporates the pertinent allowing innovations of the 4.zero age.

Kusbianto et al provided a starter see in remote components for enhancing the store network for aquaculture savvy environmental factors exceptionally vegetables request and convey. From our notice, we verified that those components are practicality and rightness.

Manohar et al progressed different harvests whose ideal attributes are taken care of in cloud, assuming any of the limits is going amazing or low it's miles restricted through hub mcu that is interacted with IOT. The need of IOT is to transport the recuperated measurements to the net (mass storing) and PC knows about introducing the contemporary popularity to the client by means of net with the reason that checking and support will get less complicated wireless.

Moreno et al orientated to making arrangements a wi-ficient profound water lifestyle tank-farming device that recovers water resources and produces under restricted natural circumstances.

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The hydroponics structures needed to hold the PH ranges, temperature, water flow level, and humidity outcomes of the hydroponic setup. in this work, these datasets were accumulated over a length of 1 month to generate an ANN set of rules closer to execution prognostic evaluation for giving output choice for unconventionally monitoring the system. also, the gadget presents IOT net for showing, tracking and controlling the actuators from aquicultural ranches.

Figure 1 proposed system

Artificial neural networks (ANN) algorithm

ANN is developed after the gaining knowledge of capabilities of the social mind so it can apprehend styles and expect. Neural network is are shaped from neurons that are analogous to features of the human brain for numerous reasons. in the brain, a neuron sends out an electrical sign thru a strand known as an axon, which splits into many branches [1]. at the stop of every branch, there is an area referred to as a synapse. An ANN is like the working of the brain since there are weighted associations (relate to neurotransmitters) between reproduced neurons where pointers it gets (numbers) are added after which (with most neuron forms) a sign is sent (terminated) assuming a definite limit is reached. There are extraordinary brain network plans by which information is handled in unique habits. The most utilized kind of ANN today is nonlinear feed ahead and through far the greatest popular feed forward kind is lower back spread.

Feed Forward Back Propagation Method

On this developed model, the maximum commonplace neural community architectures, the feed forward lower back propagation NN. This neural network architecture could be very regular, because it can be implemented to many one-of-a-kind responsibilities. the primary time period, 'feed forward' designates how this neural network procedures and recalls patterns [2]. The term 'returned propagation' declares how this sort of neural network is educated. back propagation is a shape of supervised training steps concerned in education

1) Information Collection:

The all information related to crop manufacturing based on plant nutrients and different parameter is accrued from agricultural schools.

2) Build the prediction model:

- discover the top of the line configuration of neural a. network by combining many distinctive ANN prototypes.
- The number of hidden layers and schooling parameters were obtained via trial and error technique.
- Loading of NN and strictures by adjusting the momentum

Figure 2 ANN model

On the premise of education parameter, we train the ANN the parameters like pH, temperature, humidity and flow sensor are given to predict the hydroponics setup the usage of artificial Neural community.

HARDWARE DESCRIPTION

a) **ARDUINO Controller**

Arduino is a microcontroller or it very well may be alluded to as device for causing PC frameworks which can to feel and oversee more noteworthy of the physical and genuine world than your PC. it is actual figuring stage fundamentally founded on a basic microcontroller board, and an improvement climate for composing programming for the board Arduino can be utilized to increment intelligent contraptions, taking contributions from a choice of switches or sensors, and controlling a spread of lighting, vehicles, and other real results. Arduino errands tend to independent, or they might be assisted with the guide of the product area strolling on your PC. The sheets can be collected through hand or bought preassembled from the market, it is accessible very without issues. The arduino IDE is the product program stage which might be downloaded without spending a dime. The Arduino programming language is an execution of Wiring and characterizing the contraptions utilized, a comparable substantial registering stage, which depends on the Processing sight and sound programming environmental elements.

b) **Water float sensor**

It incorporates a plastic valve from which water can skip. A water rotor alongside a lobby influence sensor is available the experience and degree the water stream. while water streams through the valve it turns the rotor. through this, the trade might be found in the speed of the engine.

c) **Temperature Sensor (LM35):**

LM35 is an accuracy IC temperature sensor with its result relative to the temperature (in oC). The sensor hardware is fixed and thusly it isn't exposed to oxidation and various procedures. With LM35, temperature might be estimated extra accurately than with a thermistor. It likewise own low self warming and doesn't reason more than 0.1 oC temperature climb in any case air. The having fever range is from - fifty five°C to 150°C. The result voltage changes by means of 10mV in response to each oC up push/decrease in surrounding temperature, i.e., its scale angle is zero.01V/oC.

d) **PH sensor**

A pH sensor is one of the most extreme fundamental stuff that is typically utilized for water estimations. This sort of sensor can gauge the amount of alkalinity and corrosiveness in water and different responses.

e) **Dampness sensor**

Dampness is the presence of water in air. how much water fume in air can meaningfully affect human encouragement notwithstanding many assembling techniques in enterprises. The presence of water fume likewise influences assorted physical, synthetic, and natural strategies. Dampness sensors work by distinguishing adjustments that alter electric flows or temperature inside the air. There are 3 fundamental types of mugginess sensors: capacitive, resistive and warm. Every one of the three sorts will screen minute changes inside the environment which will ascertain the stickiness inside the air.

IOT PROGRAMMING PROTOCOL

a) **HTTP Protocol**

Hypertext switch Protocol (HTTP) is a connectionless client/server convention pervasive in IT and the web. because of the reality there are interminable open stockpile gear that utilization HTTP, and each coding language has HTTP libraries, it's far extremely helpful. the point of convergence on HTTP in IoT is around Representational nation move (unwinding), which is a stateless model wherein clients can get section to sources on the server through demands. In many examples, an asset is a gadget and the records that a gadget incorporates. HTTP gives a delivery, but doesn't frame the introduction of the data. All things considered, HTTP solicitations can contain HTML, JavaScript, JavaScript thing Notation (JSON), XML, and others. In many cases, IoT is normalizing around JSON over HTTP. HTTP verbal trade is normally settled over TCP/IP associations. HTTP can be also set up various convention, including inconsistent UDP.

b) **Fluid Crystal show (lcd)**

LCDs are for the most part utilized for movable electronic computer games, as viewfinders for advanced cameras and camcorders, in video projection frameworks, for computerized bulletins, as video show units for PCs, and in level board TVs.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a smart IoT based totally hydroponic device is advanced. The sensor parameters are used to control the system with the usage of ANN towards imparting the correct manipulate movement which is labeled. This paramters are tuned by the layer operations of ANN for autonomous control. The predicted manage movement for the real-time information is stored in the cloud. The arduino controller acts as the threshold wherein the ANN version deployed for generating the expected output and speaking with the Arduino. This has been advanced as a prototype.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Manohar, V. K. Sundari, A. E. Pious, A. Beno, L. D. V. Anand and D. Ravikumar, "IoT based Automation of Hydroponics using Node MCU Interface," 2021 Third International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA), 2021, pp. 32-36, doi: 10.1109/ICIRCA51532.2021.9544637.
- [2] M. C. Moreno, O. J. Suarez and A. P. Garcia, "IoT-based Automated Greenhouse for Deep Water Culture Hydroponic System," 2021 2nd Sustainable Cities Latin America Conference (SCLA), 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/SCLA53004.2021.9540187.
- [3] A. Dutta, I. Nag, S. Basu, D. Seal and R. K. Gayen, "IoT based Indoor Hydroponics System," 2021 5th International Conference on Electronics, Materials Engineering & Nano-Technology (IEMENTech), 2021, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1109/IEMENTech53263.2021.9614730.
- [4] Sahara, R. H. Saputra, M. Asis and A. Lawasnitro, "Design of Hydroponic Planting Media Based on Solar Cell Power," 2021 7th International Conference on Electrical, Electronics and Information Engineering (ICEEIE), 2021, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICEEIE52663.2021.9616657.
- [5] D. Kusbianto Purwoko Aji, A. Datumaya Wahyudi Sumari, B. Satria Andoko and H. Pradibta, "Preliminary Study to Optimize the Supply Chain of the PT. Otsuka-Built Hydroponics Smart Ecosystem," 2021 International Conference on Electrical and Information Technology (IEIT), 2021, pp. 87-91, doi: 10.1109/IEIT53149.2021.9587390.
- [6] S. López-Tejeida, L. Felix-Cuencas, J. J. De León-Ramirez, L. B. Flores-Tejeida, M. Villegas-Villegas and J. F. García-Trejo, "Methods to measure nitrogen content in fish culture: A review," 2021 XVII International Engineering Congress (CONIIN), 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/CONIIN54356.2021.9634790.
- [7] M. Friuli, A. Masciullo, F. S. Blasi, M. Mita, L. Corbari and I. Surano, "A 4.0 Sustainable Aquaponic System Based on the Combined Use of Superabsorbing Natural Hydrogels and Innovative Sensing Technologies for the Optimization of Water Use," 2021 IEEE 6th International Forum on Research and Technology for Society and Industry (RTSI), 2021, pp. 429-434, doi: 10.1109/RTSI50628.2021.9597250.
- [8] H. C. Quach, H. Hiscott, H. Mazanec and S. B. Mehta, "Assessing the Feasibility of Microgrid Supported Open Hydroponics (MSOHCC) for A Resilient Fresh Food Supply in SIDS," 2021 Systems and Information Engineering Design Symposium (SIEDS), 2021, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/SIEDS52267.2021.9483713.
- [9] K. Tatas, A. Al-Zoubi, A. Antoniou and D. Zolotareva, "iPONICS: IoT Monitoring and Control for Hydroponics," 2021 10th International Conference on Modern Circuits and Systems Technologies (MOCASST), 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/MOCASST52088.2021.9493387.
- [10] D. R. Sahu, A. I. Mukadam, S. D. Das and S. Das, "Integration of Machine Learning and IoT System for Monitoring Different Parameters and Optimizing farming," 2021 International Conference on Intelligent Technologies (CONIT), 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/CONIT51480.2021.9498474.
- [11] E. D. Nugroho, A. G. Putrada and A. Rakhmatsyah, "Predictive Control on Lettuce NFT-based Hydroponic IoT using Deep Neural Network," 2021 International Symposium on Electronics and Smart Devices (ISESD), 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ISESD53023.2021.9501402.
- [12] U. Arora, S. Shetty, R. Shah and D. K. Sinha, "Automated Dosing System in Hydroponics with Machine Learning," 2021 International Conference on Communication information and Computing Technology (ICCICT), 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICCICT50803.2021.9510115.
- [13] R. S. Al-Gharibi, "IoT-Based Hydroponic System," 2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN), 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICSCAN53069.2021.9526391.
- [14] E. Y. Fitria, M. A. Murti and C. Setianingsih, "Design of Integrated Control System Based On IoT With Context Aware Method In Hydroponic Plants," 2021 IEEE International Conference on Industry 4.0, Artificial Intelligence, and Communications Technology (IAICT), 2021, pp. 20-26, doi: 10.1109/IAICT52856.2021.9532550.
- [15] J. John and M. P. R, "Automated Fish Feed Detection in IoT Based Aquaponics System," 2021 8th International Conference on Smart Computing and Communications (ICSCC), 2021, pp. 286-290, doi: 10.1109/ICSCC51209.2021.9528186.